

Fig. 1: Consensus clustering reveals distinct proteome subtypes

Fig. 1: Consensus clustering reveals distinct proteome subtypes. **a**, Principal component analysis of MS data overlaid with PAM50 subtypes. **b**, Principal component analysis of MS data overlaid with identified consensus clusters. **c**, Alluvial plot of consensus clusters and corresponding PAM50 subtypes. **d**, GSEA of consensus clusters using Hallmark gene sets showing NES of gene sets with FDR < 0.1. **e**, RPPA pathway activity scores in consensus proteome subtypes. * p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.00; NES: Normalized enrichment score

Fig. 2: Clinical outcomes in consensus proteome subtypes

Fig. 2: Clinical outcomes in consensus proteome subtypes. Fraction of **(a)** pCR (purple) and **(b)** responders (purple) in proteome clusters separated by treatment arm. Response was defined as pCR for TNBC cases and as RCB 0/1 for ER-positive cases. The number of patients in each group is printed in the bars. **c**, Event-free survival in proteome clusters separated by treatment arm. **d**, Overall survival in proteome clusters separated by treatment arm. * $p < 0.05$

Fig. 3: Treatment induced changes in protein signaling

Fig. 3: Treatment induced changes in protein signaling. **a**, Median GSVA score of Hallmark gene sets depicted as line plots across timepoints and separated by treatment arm and proteome subtype. Circle sizes are inversely proportional to the standard deviation. **b**, RPPA pathway activity score of INF signaling in consensus proteome subtypes. **c**, Median GSVA score of Hallmark gene sets depicted as line plots across timepoints and separated by responders (R) and non-responders (NR) in proteome subtypes. * $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 4: DNA damage repair mechanisms in proteome subtypes

Fig. 4: DNA damage repair mechanisms in proteome subtypes. **a**, Fraction of genomic HRD-positive tumors (turquoise) and HRD score in consensus proteome clusters. **c,d**, RPPA pathway activity scores of DNA damage checkpoint (**c**) and repair (**d**) in consensus proteome subtypes. **d**, Median GSVA score of Hallmark gene sets across two timepoints, separated by treatment arm and consensus proteome subtype. Circle sizes are inversely proportional to the standard deviation. **e**, Volcanoplots comparing RPPA protein expression in responders to Cb+NACT with stromal-enriched subtype vs. basal-enriched subtype. DNA repair proteins highlighted in red and DNA damage checkpoint proteins in blue. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; FC: fold change; HRD: homologous recombination deficiency.

Fig. 5: Identification of proteome clusters in NeoAva

Fig. 5: Identification of proteome clusters in NeoAva. **a**, RPPA core reactive versus hormone receptor activity score overlaid with PAM50 subtype. **b**, RPPA core reactive and hormone receptor in identified proteome subtypes. **c**, RPPA activity scores in identified proteome subtypes. **d**, Volcanoplots comparing protein expression in basal- and stromal-enriched tumors. DNA repair proteins highlighted in red and DNA damage checkpoint proteins in blue. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; FC: fold change.

Supplementary Fig. S1: k-means consensus clustering

Supplementary Fig. S1: k-means consensus clustering. a, Consensus matrices for k=2-6. **b**, Tracking plot **c**, CDF area and change in CDF area.

Supplementary Fig. S2: Consensus proteome subtypes in RPPA dataset

Supplementary Fig. S2: Consensus proteome subtypes in RPPA data. Principal component analysis of RPPA data overlaid with **a**, ER status, **b**, PAM50 subtypes, **c**, identified consensus proteome subtypes

Supplementary Fig. S3: RCB 0/1 in consensus proteome subtypes

Supplementary Fig. S3: RCB 0/1 in consensus proteome subtypes. a, Fraction of RCB 0/1 in consensus proteome subtypes separated by treatment arm. The number of patients in each group is printed in the bars.

Supplementary Fig. S4: HRD score in responders and non-responders

Supplementary Fig. S4: HRD score in responders and non-responders. Genomic HRD score in responders and non-responders in patients treated with **a** Cb+NACT and **b**, NACT alone. R: responder; NR: non-responder.

Supplementary Fig. S5: Identification of proteome clusters in NeoAva

Supplementary Fig. S5: Validation of proteome clusters in NeoAva. a, Principal component analysis of NeoAva RPPA data overlaid with identified proteome subtypes.

Supplementary Fig. S6: Consensus clustering of CPTAC dataset

Supplementary Fig. S6: Consensus clustering of CPTAC dataset. a, Consensus matrices for k=2-6. **b**, Tracking plot **c**, CDF area and change in CDF area.

Supplementary Table S1: Proteins included in pathway activity score calculation

Pathway	Protein	Weight
G2M checkpoint	Cyclin-B1	1
	CDK1_pT14	1
	Rb_pS807_S811	1
	PLK1	1
	Cdc25C	1
Hormone receptors	ER_alpha	1
	ER_alpha_pS118	1
	PR	1
	AR	1
Core reactive	Caveolin-1	1
	bCatenin	-1
	RBM15	-1
	ECadherin	-1
	Claudin-7	-1
EMT	Fibronectin	1
	NCadherin	1
	Collagen-VI	1
	Caludin-7	-1
	ECadherin	-1
	bCatenin	-1
	PAI-1	1
INF signaling	Stat1_pY701	1
	HLA-DQA1	1
	HLA-DR-DP-DQ-DX	1
	PD-L1	1
	IDO	1
	B7-H3	-1
	STING	1
	cGAS	1
	DNA damage checkpoint	ATM_pS1981
ATR_pS428		1
Cdc2_pY15		1
Chk1_pS296		0.5
Ckh1_pS345		0.5
Chk2_pT68		1
Wee1_pS642		1
DNA damage repair	53BP1	1
	ERCC1	1
	ERCC5	1
	PARP	1
	Rad50	1
	Rad51	1
	XRCC1	1
	ATRAX	1
	PAR	1
	RRM1	1
RRM2	1	

Supplementary Table S2: Clinical characteristics for the consensus proteome clusters in the I-BCT cohort.

Characteristics	Basal-enriched (n = 59)		Luminal-enriched (n = 71)		Stromal-enriched (n = 29)	
	Cb+NACT	NACT	Cb+NACT	NACT	Cb+NACT	NACT
Treatment arm						
Number of patients	33	31	38	33	12	17
Age at diagnosis (median)	46	46	47	47	54	52
Stage						
cT2	22	24	25	19	11	8
cT3	10	5	12	13	0	8
cT4	1	2	1	1	1	1
IHC subtype						
HER2-, ER+, PR+	0	2	34	26	4	7
HER2-, ER+, PR-	11	3	4	5	2	5
HER2-, ER-, PR-	22	26	0	2	6	5
PAM50 subtype						
Luminal A	0	1	22	20	5	10
Luminal B	1	1	14	9	1	1
Basal-like	31	28	1	0	5	3
Her2-enriched	1	1	1	4	0	2
Normal-like	0	0	0	0	1	1
HRD status						
HRD	23	24	2	5	3	4
Not HRD	9	7	35	28	5	12
Missing	1	0	1	0	4	1
RCB status						
RCB 0	22	11	2	5	6	3
RCB 1	3	7	6	1	2	2
RCB 2	7	7	25	15	3	10
RCB 3	1	4	5	12	1	1
Missing	0	2*	0	0	0	1*
Event status						
Event	5	8	9	6	0	5
No event	28	23	29	27	12	12

*Progression during neoadjuvant treatment period